

Experimental analysis of freezing times for fish and dummy loads in a horizontal CO₂ plate freezer at -50 °C evaporation temperature

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ABSTRACT

This study experimentally evaluated the performance of an industrial-scale horizontal CO₂ plate freezer integrated into an existing CO₂ refrigeration system. The shared central CO₂ system can provide cooling capacity of 100 kW at evaporation temperature between -30 °C and -50 °C. Apple juice cartons were employed as the primary test material acting as dummy loads; freezing times were also measured for real fish samples—including mackerel, herring, and salmon. Freezing trials with apple juice cartons showed that lowering the average evaporation temperature from -36.1 °C to -48.6 °C reduced the average freezing time by 35.3%. Although the Coefficient of Performance (COP) was lower at reduced evaporation temperatures, specific energy consumption remained largely unaffected because of shorter freezing times. Additionally, lower circulation rates were associated with longer freezing time and higher specific energy consumption. The experimental results also demonstrated the importance of uniform plate contact, packaging material and configuration, and optimized product void space for freezing efficiency. A dynamic numerical model was developed and validated against the experimental data, showing good agreement with observed temperature profiles and freezing times.

1. Introduction

Food loss and waste are a worldwide concern that undermines the sustainability of the food system. It was estimated that at least 6 % of worldwide greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions can be traced back to food that is lost or wasted throughout the supply chain (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2015). According to FAO estimates, approximately 35 % of fish, 30 % of cereals, 40–50 % of root crops, fruits and vegetables, and 20 % of oilseeds, meat and dairy products are lost or wasted at various stages from production to consumption (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2015). In fish processing, reducing food loss and waste requires the adoption of effective cooling and freezing technologies to preserve product quality and extend shelf life. This, in turn, can help lower both energy consumption and associated GHG emissions.

Freezing is one of the most common methods used in the food industry to preserve the quality of fish and meat products during large-scale processing and extended storage periods. Freezing methods are generally categorized into three types: contact freezing, immersion freezing, and air blast freezing. Plate freezing, a type of contact freezing, cools products by placing them in direct contact with parallel metal

plates through which a refrigerant or secondary coolant circulates. Horizontal plate freezers are well-suited for flat, packaged, or block-shaped products, such as boxed fillets, or meat blocks, minimizing product deformation and enabling high-efficiency operations. These systems are adaptable to batch, semi-continuous, and continuous operations. A report for the Australian Meat Research Corporation (Graham, 1996) showed that when cartoned meat was frozen below -10 °C using a coolant temperature of -30 °C, plate freezing reduced the freezing time by up to 36 % compared with air-blast freezing. Similarly, plate freezing shortened the freezing time of Indian mackerel by over 51 % relative to air-blast freezing—a reduction that can significantly contribute to preserving fish quality during freezing by minimizing the formation of fat-oxidized products and histamine (Lakshminisha et al., 2008). The double-sided contact design of plate freezers ensures quick and uniform freezing, helping to retain the product's quality, flavor, and nutritional value while also enhancing yield. Moreover, plate freezers offer substantial energy savings compared to traditional air blast freezing (Graham, 1996), making them an energy efficient option for large-scale fish and meat processing.

Growing environmental concerns have prompted the gradual restriction or complete elimination of numerous synthetic refrigerants. As

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Fig. 1. Simplified schematic diagram of the plate freezing system and the corresponding p-h diagram of the cycle.

a result, freezing technologies that utilise natural refrigerants—characterized by low or zero Global Warming Potential (GWP) and no Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)—are gaining momentum as sustainable and future-proof solutions, drawing increasing attention from industry and regulators alike. Ammonia remains the most widely used refrigerant in horizontal plate freezer systems, valued for its efficiency and low

environmental impact. However, its application to achieve evaporation temperatures below $-35\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ requires sub-atmospheric pressure operation, and its thermal efficiency can decline significantly as the evaporation temperature decreases.

In contrast, using CO₂ as a refrigerant enables freezer evaporation temperatures to reach down to $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, significantly reducing freezing

Fig. 2. CO₂ plate freezing system in the lab, (a) plate freezer, (b) separator, subcooler, and expansion valve (V3).

time and enhancing overall processing efficiency. Shorter freezing times not only allow larger quantities of fish or meat to be processed per unit time but also benefit product quality by minimizing the waiting period before loading into the freezer. According to the numerical study by Ren, et al. (S. Ren et al., 2024), the freezing time in a horizontal CO₂ plate freezer can be reduced by approximately 43 % when the evaporation temperature is decreased from $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Fernández-Seara, et al. (Fernández-Seara et al., 2012) achieved a minimum evaporation temperature of $-50.07\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in their experimental study on water freezing in a horizontal CO₂ plate freezer. By lowering the average evaporation temperature from $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $-45\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the freezing time was reduced by up to 11.7 %, with a decrease in the system COP from 1.34 to 1.20. Verpe, et al. (Verpe et al., 2018) reported a freezing time of 95.7 min for agar-gel with a thickness of 103 mm using a CO₂ vertical plate freezer operating at an evaporation temperature of $-49\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The freezing time can be further reduced by optimizing the circulation ratio to enhance the heat transfer through the plate surfaces (S. Ren et al., 2024). Therefore, CO₂ plate freezers can achieve high operational efficiency and benefit from high heat transfer performance (Saeed, 2020). CO₂ also exhibits a lower saturation temperature change per unit pressure loss ($\Delta T_{\text{sat}}/\Delta P$), a characteristic that confers a notable advantage with respect to system efficiency compared to the ammonia system (Verpe, 2018). In addition, compared with air blast freezers, CO₂ plate freezers require less frequent defrosting and can maintain excellent food quality by minimizing dehydration (Kenneth et al., 1997). Beyond its technical advantages, CO₂ is also with low toxicity and non-flammable, enhancing its safety profile. Thanks to this combination of operational efficiency, safety, and environmental performance, CO₂ plate freezing technology holds strong commercial appeal and aligns well with the growing demand for greener and more reliable food processing methods.

Although the adoption of the CO₂ horizontal plate freezer in the fish industry has been growing in some European countries in recent years, research on this technology remains scarce. Understanding how

operating and structural parameters affect the freezing performance is crucial for improving system efficiency and minimizing environmental impact. In addition, although many freezing time prediction correlations have been proposed in the past decades, most of which were based on the Plank's equation (Kenneth et al., 1997), these empirical formulas are limited to providing rough approximations of freezing time and are unable to deliver accurate predictions across different system operating conditions. As numerical simulation tools continue to evolve, dynamic numerical models are capable of performing comprehensive simulations of freezing systems, enabling more accurate predictions of freezing time as well as the dynamic system performance with low computation cost. Nevertheless, dedicated predictive tools for plate freezing systems are currently lacking. To address these gaps and evaluate the capabilities and real-world performance of a horizontal CO₂ plate freezer, a test rig was designed and constructed at NTNU by integrating a real-sized industrial plate freezer into an existing CO₂ refrigeration system (S. Ren et al., 2024). The shared central CO₂ system can provide cooling capacity of 100 kW at evaporation temperature between $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The present study aimed to assess the performance of the freezing system, including freezing times for various products at different evaporation temperatures. The thermal efficiency of the freezing process was also analyzed. Furthermore, a numerical model was established to predict freezing time, supporting system design and optimization, while providing an estimation tool for industrial applications. The model's simulation results were subsequently validated against experimental data.

2. CO₂ plate freezing system at NTNU

The simplified schematic diagram of the CO₂ plate freezing system and the corresponding p-h diagram are illustrated in Fig. 1. The details of the system and its components have been described in our previous work (S. Ren et al., 2024); therefore, only a brief overview is provided

Fig. 3. Description of the plate arrangement.

Fig. 4. CO₂ circuits inside a plate (blue dashed lines) and plan view of the tested apple juice blocks in station 2.

here. The plate freezer, shown in Fig. 2(a), is an industrial-sized unit with dimensions of 2×3 m, manufactured by Optimar AS. The existing CO₂ refrigeration system supplies liquid CO₂ from the receiver at approximately 14 °C and 50 bar. The liquid CO₂ enters the separator, as shown in Fig. 2(b), through an expansion valve, where it is throttled to the target evaporation temperature. It is then pumped through the plate freezer. Inside the freezer, CO₂ evaporates by absorbing the heat from the product, and the resulting two-phase mixture returns to the separator. The vapor-phase CO₂ is subsequently directed back to the compressor suction line of the main CO₂ system, and the liquid-phase is recirculated to the plate freezer. The height difference between the separator and the pump is 4.6 m. During experimental operation, the liquid level above the pump was maintained constant by adjusting the opening degree of the expansion valve. On this basis, the mass flow rate of CO₂ exiting the freezing system (back to the compressor suction line) can be deemed equivalent to that of CO₂ entering the system via the expansion valve. After the experiment is completed, the CO₂ in the plate freezing system will be directed back to the receivers of the central CO₂ system to prevent the high standstill pressure.

Fig. 3 illustrates the configuration of the plate freezer, which is equipped with four horizontal plates, creating three product-holding stations. Each plate contains four parallel CO₂ circuits that are evenly distributed throughout its interior, as shown in Fig. 4. For testing purposes, the central compartment (Station 2) served as the main experimental zone, where the tested products were placed. To replicate realistic thermal loading conditions, Stations 1 and 3 were filled with apple juice cartons. The spacing between the plates, which defines the vertical clearance of each station, is regulated by a hydraulic mechanism working in tandem with corner-mounted spacers. This design allows adjustment of station height and ensures uniform compression across the product surfaces. Adequate contact pressure is essential for enhancing thermal conduction between the plates and the product.

3. Experimental methodology

3.1. Test products

In this study, the freezing times of various products were measured under different evaporation temperatures. Apple juice cartons were selected as the primary test material acting as dummy loads, due to their size, uniform shape, and ease of preparation. Freezing times were also examined for whole mackerel, whole herring, herring fillets, salmon fillets, and salmon portions to provide practical insights for industrial applications.

Fig. 5. Apple juice block with packaging.

Each apple juice carton had a volume of 1.5 liters and a total mass of 1.625 kg, including 0.049 kg attributed to the packaging material. The cartons were arranged in rectangular aluminum trays measuring 600 mm \times 400 mm to form a test product block. Each block consisted of two layers of apple juice cartons, reaching a total height of 133 mm. A total of 16 cartons were arranged in each tray, all enclosed within a plastic bag, as shown in Fig. 5. The aluminum tray had a thickness of 1 mm and a mass of 0.9 ± 0.005 kg.

3.2. Description of experiment

Before each test, the products were stored in a cooling room to ensure they reached the desired initial temperature. Thermocouples were inserted into the designated test locations of the product blocks prior to testing, and the blocks were sealed in plastic bags to prevent potential contamination and leakage onto the plates, in the case of apple juice tests, to protect the cartons from moisture damage caused by melted water after the test. The test procedure began with opening the expansion valve, and once a sufficient liquid level had formed above the pump, the pump was started. When the temperature at the plate freezer inlet reached the target evaporation temperature, the test products were manually loaded into Station 2. Thermocouples were then connected to the data acquisition system, and data logging was initiated. All measurement variables—including CO₂ temperature, pressure, and mass flow rate at each state point in the circuit, as shown in Fig. 1, along with the product and plate surface temperatures—were recorded at 2-minute intervals throughout the test.

Fig. 6. (a) Plan view of one apple juice block with the measurement locations, (b) side view of one apple juice block in Station 2 with measurement locations.

Table 1
Test details for fish products.

Test No.	Product	Product height (mm)	Number of blocks	Block weight (kg)
A	Whole herring	100	1	20.5
	Herring fillets		1	21.5
B	Whole mackerel	100	3	15 – 19
	Whole herring		2	17 – 20
	Herring fillets		3	17 – 22.5
C	Whole mackerel	75	3	9.5 – 13.1
	Whole herring		3	10 – 15
	Herring fillets		3	11.5 – 16.5
D	Salmon fillets	100	3	8.8 – 17.2
	Salmon portions		4	10

The compressors in the CO₂ refrigeration system operated based on the preset suction pressure. During the test, the expansion valve opening was adjusted to maintain a stable liquid level above the pump. The CO₂ mass flow rate supplied to the plate freezer was regulated by controlling the pump speed. In this study, the target freezing temperature was set at –18 °C. The test was completed once all temperature measurement points reached this temperature, after which the pump was switched off and the expansion valve was fully closed. The system is equipped with a hot-gas defrosting unit, supplied by a defrosting compressor, to facilitate product removal. During the experiments, however, defrosting was not necessary to unload the products from the freezing station, which contributed to lower overall energy consumption. In addition, the sub-cooler was deactivated during the experiments because the CO₂ refrigeration system could provide sufficient cooling capacity and supply subcooled CO₂ to the plate freezing system, making additional sub-cooling unnecessary.

Five tests were conducted using apple juice cartons. In each test, a total of nine product blocks were loaded into Station 2, with a total mass of 234 kg. A plan view of the apple juice blocks in Station 2 is illustrated in Fig. 4. Thermocouples were inserted at the center of the two stacked layers of cartons to measure core temperatures during freezing. A plan view of one of the product blocks is shown in Fig. 6(a), and a side view of a product block is shown in Fig. 6(b) with the thermocouples trapped between the upper and lower layers of cartons.

Four tests were conducted for the fish products, with details summarized in Table 1. In Test A, one block of whole herring and one block

of herring fillets were tested by packaging the fish products in plastic bags and placing them within a stainless-steel frame. The blocks were loaded into the central area of Station 2. Six thermocouples per block were inserted into the centers of the fish or fillets placed at mid-height of the frame to assess freezing uniformity. In Tests B and C, freezing times for whole mackerel, whole herring, and herring fillets were measured using frame heights of 100 mm and 75 mm, respectively. The weight of each product block varied slightly, with some packed more tightly than others, as presented in Table 1. For each product block, two thermocouples were inserted into the centres of two fish or fillets positioned at mid-height of the frame. In Test D, salmon fillets and portions were individually vacuum-packed in plastic bags and placed in cardboard boxes. As presented in Table 1, three boxes of salmon fillets were loaded into Station 2: two fully filled and one-half-filled. Four thermocouples were installed in each block: two at the center, one at the top, and one at the bottom.

3.3. Data reduction

The thermal properties used for the data analysis were obtained from REFPROP (DLL Version 10.0) (Lemmon et al., 2018). The instantaneous freezing load of the plate freezer was calculated by Eq. (1), with the state point numbers corresponding to those shown in Fig. 1, using the mass flow rate of CO₂ entering the plate freezing system and the enthalpy difference between the CO₂ exiting and entering the system; this value corresponds to the heat extracted from the frozen product through the evaporation of CO₂ within the freezer.

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{freezing}} = \dot{m}_3(h_7 - h_3) \quad (1)$$

The instantaneous power consumption of the freezing system could not be directly determined from the measurement data, as the CO₂ refrigeration unit was simultaneously used to supply other test facilities. Instead, the power consumption was estimated based on the suction conditions and the compressor isentropic efficiency (η_{isen}), which ranged from 0.625 to 0.675 and was derived in accordance with the operation conditions and the manufacturer's technical data (Bitzer Software. v7.1.2.6., 2025). The pump's power consumption during the experiments was approximately 0.05–0.2 kW, considered negligible, and therefore excluded from the calculations. The power consumption of the compressors was calculated as

$$\dot{W}_{\text{com}} = \dot{m}_3(h_8 - h_7) \quad (2)$$

Table 2
Uncertainties of measured and calculated quantities.

Quantity	Uncertainty
Temperature of CO ₂ (°C)	± 0.15
Product temperature (°C)	± 1
Pressure (bar)	± 0.25 %
Differential pressure (mbar)	± 0.05 %
Mass flow rate (kg/s)	± 0.2 %
Freezing load (kW)	± 0.23 % (calculated)
Power consumption (kW)	± 0.43 % (calculated)
COP (-)	± 0.40 % (calculated)

$$h_8 = \frac{h_{isen} - h_7}{\eta_{isen}} + h_7 \quad (3)$$

The instantaneous COP of the system can then be calculated as

$$COP = \dot{Q}_{freezing} / \dot{W}_{com} \quad (4)$$

The cumulative COP_{cum} over the entire freezing process was calculated as

$$COP_{cum} = \frac{\int \dot{Q}_{freezing} dt}{\int \dot{W}_{com} dt} \quad (5)$$

3.4. Uncertainties

The pressure, temperature, and mass flow rates of CO₂ at various locations in the plate freezing system were measured using different instruments, while the product's core temperature was monitored with Type T thermocouples. Details of the system's instrumentation were provided by Ren, et al. (S. Ren et al., 2024). The uncertainty (U) of the calculated quantities was determined according to Eq.(6) (Taylor, 2009), and calculated using the software EES (Klein, 2020). The uncertainties of both the measured and calculated values are summarized in Table 2.

$$U_Y = \sqrt{\sum_i \left(\frac{\partial Y}{\partial X_i} \right)^2 \cdot U_{X_i}^2} \quad (6)$$

4. Numerical model

In addition to the experimental work, a dynamic numerical model of the CO₂ plate freezing system was established using Dymola (Dynamic Modelling Library, version 2022) (Systèmes, 2022) with the Modelica programming language. The simulations employed two commercial Modelica libraries — TIL Suite 3.10.0 and TILMedia 3.10.0 — developed by TLK-Thermo GmbH (Schultze, 2013; TLK-Thermo 2021). Both the overall system model and the individual component models were based on the plate freezing system described in Section 2, as shown in Fig. 1. As these models have been thoroughly presented in our earlier publication (S. Ren et al., 2024), only a concise overview is provided here. As the subcooler was not employed during the experiments, it was accordingly deactivated in the simulation. The boundary conditions applied in the simulation—namely, the supply liquid CO₂ temperature and pressure at state point 1, and the vapor CO₂ temperature and pressure at state point

7 returning to the compressor suction line—were derived from the average values obtained in the experiments.

The plate freezer was represented in the simulation as a tube heat exchanger with a capacitor heat boundary, allowing the modeling of heat transfer from the product at its initial temperature and for varying product masses. The evaporation heat transfer coefficient was determined using the correlation proposed by Gungor and Winterton (Gungor and Winterton, 1987), while single-phase heat transfer was evaluated using the correlations of Gnielinski (Gnielinski, 1975) and Dittus and Boelter (Dittus and Boelter, 1985). The pressure drop was estimated according to the Konakov (Konakov, 1946) correlation.

Since ice in fish products forms over a temperature range rather than at a single point, the simulation applied a temperature-dependent effective heat capacity that accounts for both sensible and latent heat effects, following Schwartzberg (Schwartzberg, 1976). The frozen product was modeled as a homogeneous material with a regular shape. No specific geometry was assumed beyond a total volume with uniform temperature for the entire volume. In the absence of specific data, the effective heat capacity of herring fillets was approximated using the parameters for cod muscle reported by Schwartzberg (Schwartzberg, 1976). A packaging factor of 3.5 was incorporated into the correlation to account for the effects of packaging materials and void spaces. For apple juice, due to the absence of data for the test apple juice, the thermal properties of water were adopted as approximation, also with a packaging factor of 3.5.

5. Results and discussions

5.1. Freezing time measured with different evaporation temperatures

Multiple tests were carried out to measure the freezing time for apple juice cartons under different evaporation temperatures, with the details summarized in Table 3. Minor variations in the initial temperature (T_{start}) of the product blocks were observed, caused by uneven cooling room conditions and the time lag associated with loading the blocks individually. The average evaporation temperature ($T_{e,ave}$) was determined as the mean of the evaporation temperatures corresponding to the pressures at the inlet and outlet of the plate freezer during each test. The inlet pressure was measured at the inlet of Plate 2 and the outlet pressure was calculated by subtracting the measured pressure drop across Plate 2 from the measured inlet pressure. The circulation rate (CR) is defined as the ratio of the refrigerant mass flow rate circulated through the freezer to the vapor mass flow rate leaving the freezer and can be expressed as \dot{m}_5 / \dot{m}_3 . The CO₂ mass flow rate supplied to the plate freezer was primarily controlled by pump speed but was also influenced by the liquid level above the pump. In Tests 01, 02, 04, and 05, the pump operated at 15 % of its maximum speed, whereas in Test 03 it was set to 10 %. The average CR (CR_{ave}) values for each test are summarized in Table 3.

The CO₂ temperatures recorded at the inlet and outlet of the plate freezer in Test 01 are presented in Fig. 7. Throughout the freezing process, the CO₂ temperature across the plate freezer was maintained between -50 °C and -48 °C, with the outlet temperature slightly lower than the inlet pressure due to the pressure loss. Given that the outlet temperature was measured downstream of the flexible hoses—which connect the plates to the header and enable the hydraulic system to

Table 3
Freezing time tests conducted for apple juice cartons.

Test No.	T_{start} (°C)	$T_{e,ave}$ (°C)	CR _{ave} (-)	Average freezing time (min)	COP _{cum} (-)	Specific energy consumption (kWh·kg ⁻¹)	GHG emission (g CO _{2,eq} ·kWh ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹)	
							NO _{el}	EU _{el}
01	0 – 4.5	-48.5	6.05	335	2.47	0.067	3.35	14.1
02	1.2 – 4.4	-48.5	5.85	366	2.50	0.084	4.21	17.7
03	2.8 – 4.1	-48.8	3.36	390	2.45	0.097	4.88	20.5
04	1.5 – 3.5	-41.8	5.70	449	3.03	0.071	3.55	14.9
05	1 – 2.5	-36.1	5.57	518	3.55	0.064	3.18	13.3

Fig. 7. Evolution of the CO₂ temperature at the plate freezer inlet (T_{in}) and outlet (T_{out}), along with the temperatures of the top surface of Plate 2 ($T_{Plate\ 2}$) and the bottom surface of Plate 3 ($T_{Plate\ 3}$) during Test 01.

Fig. 8. Evolution of the CO₂ pressure at the plate freezer inlet (P_{in}), outlet of Plate 2 ($P_{out,Plate\ 2}$), freezer outlet ($P_{out,freezer}$), and separator ($P_{separator}$) during Test 01.

move the plates, a small portion of the temperature reduction was attributed to pressure loss occurring within the flexible hoses. The same evaporation temperature range as Test 01 was also maintained during Tests 02 and 03. The temperatures of the top surface of Plate 2 and the bottom surface of Plate 3 were also measured, as shown in Fig. 7. These measurements were taken from areas of the plate surfaces not covered by the test products. At the start of the test, the plate surface temperatures were slightly higher than the CO₂ temperature at the inlet and outlet, but they gradually converged toward the CO₂ temperature by the end of the test, suggesting efficient heat transfer from the CO₂ to the plate surfaces, with the product being cooled at a plate temperature very close to the evaporation temperature.

Fig. 8 illustrates the pressure at freezer inlet (P_{in}), the pressure at the

outlet of Plate 2 ($P_{out,Plate\ 2}$), the pressure measured at the freezer outlet downstream of the flexible hoses ($P_{out,freezer}$), and the pressure at the separator ($P_{separator}$) during Test 01. The pressure difference between P_{in} and $P_{out,Plate\ 2}$ —the pressure drop across Plate 2—ranged from 50 to 225 mbar. In addition, the pressure difference between $P_{out,Plate\ 2}$ and $P_{out,freezer}$, mainly attributed to the pressure loss across the flexible hoses, was between 15–80 mbar during the freezing process and associated with an insignificant temperature reduction of 0.05–0.3 K. The pressure difference from the freezer outlet to the separator was from 180 mbar to 320 mbar, corresponding to a temperature decrease of 0.6–1.1 K, which was much lower than the values observed from ammonia plate freezing system (MØNSTED and REINHOLDT, 2011).

Product Block E, located at the centre of the tested station, exhibited

Fig. 9. Evolution of the measured product centre temperature in Test-01.

the longest freezing time in Test 01, with 410 min measured at Location 1 and 420 min measured at Location 2, as shown in Fig. 9. In contrast, Product Block G had the shortest freezing time, with 284 min measured at Location 1 and 290 min measured at Location 2, as shown in Fig. 9. Generally, products placed in the middle row experienced longer freezing times. This may be attributed to the uneven spacing between the plates. The hydraulic pressure applied to the product surface was higher near the plate corners, resulting in smaller plate distances in those areas. As a result, products near the corners had better thermal contact with the plate surfaces, while those positioned closer to the centre had poorer contact, leading to the longest freezing time for the central block. However, in an industrial setting, plate spacing would not be allowed to be affected by hydraulic pressure in this manner. Industrial freezers are typically equipped with central dividers to maintain consistent spacing. Additionally, a full load of products in all stations, combined with a robust top frame capable of withstanding the pressure,

helps eliminate uneven spacing between plates. Another possible factor influencing freezing time was the trajectory of the CO₂ flow within the plates and the specific placement of each test product block.

As illustrated in Fig. 9, for all product blocks, the measured freezing times at Location 3 and 4 were longer than those at Location 1 and 2. For block G, the freezing times measured at Location 3 and 4 were 18%–36% longer than those measured at Location 1 and 2. This phenomenon was more obvious during the final phase of freezing—the cooling down of the already frozen product. The differences in freezing times within the same product block can be attributed to the packaging method using plastic bags. As shown in Fig. 5, the side where the bag was sealed with tape had a thicker and ununiform plastic layer. The plastic bag was between the apple juice carton and the plates, as shown in Fig. 6(b). This added thickness increased thermal resistance, which led to a longer freezing time for the thermocouples inserted on that side. This indicates that the packaging material and manner have a significant impact on

Fig. 10. The temperature curves at location 1 for the fastest-freezing blocks in Test 01–05.

Fig. 11. The temperature curves at location 1 for the blocks with the longest freezing times in Test 01–05.

freezing time. The core temperatures recorded at Locations 1 and 2 showed generally consistent trends, with small deviations resulting from differences in starting temperature, minor shape deformations of the cartons under the combined effects of apple juice weight and hydraulic pressure, and thermocouple precision. In Tests 02–05, thermocouples were installed only at Locations 1 and 2.

During Tests 01–05, the product blocks located near the plate corners consistently exhibited the shortest freezing times. Fig. 10 presents the temperature curves at Location 1 for these fastest-freezing blocks. In Tests 01–03, the average CO₂ evaporation temperature was maintained at approximately -48.5°C , as provided in Table 3. The shortest freezing times were consistently recorded for Block G, with values that ranging between 284 min and 318 min. Three distinct freezing stages were observed in Tests 02 and 03, whereas in Test 01 the freezing of Block G began directly from the second stage due to its lower initial temperature.

The freezing point of apple juice was approximately -1°C . After the phase change process, the center temperature of Block G dropped rapidly and reached the target core temperature. A comparison of the shortest freezing times across tests shows that reducing the average evaporation temperature from -36.1°C (Test 05) to -41.8°C (Test 04) shortened the freezing time by 17.3%. A larger decrease, from -36.1°C (Test 05) to -48.5°C (Test 01), resulted in a 40.8% reduction in freezing time.

Fig. 11 illustrates the temperature curves at Location 1 for the blocks with the longest freezing times in each test. With the exception of Test 02, the maximum freezing durations were consistently recorded for product blocks positioned in the middle row. Because the hydraulic system was controlled manually, the distribution of the hydraulic pressure applied to the plates, and the resulting plate spacing, were not consistent across all tests. This inconsistency may explain why the

Fig. 12. Evolution of the freezing load (Q) and power consumption (W) in Test 02 (red dashed lines denote fitted trendlines without physical meaning).

shortest and longest freezing times were not observed for the same product block in each test. For future research and practical operations, a hydraulic system with precise control capabilities—enabling more accurate regulation of plate spacing—should be implemented. Furthermore, as the apple juice cartons were reused after each test, minor shape deformations occurred under the combined effects of apple juice weight and hydraulic pressure. These deformations may affect the contact between the carton surfaces and the freezer plates; in turn, these effects may alter the measured freezing times and result in the long freezing time for Block A in Test 02—even though Block A was positioned close to the plate corner. In addition, Block A had highest initial temperature among the blocks in Test 02, which may also have contributed as a factor influencing its long freezing time. These impact factors should be mitigated to optimize freezing performance. As shown in Fig. 11, when the evaporation temperature was lowered from -36.1 °C in Test 05 to -41.8 °C in Test 04, the freezing time was reduced by 15.1 %. A larger decrease

in evaporation temperature, from -36.1 °C in Test 05 to -48.5 °C in Tests 01, shortened the freezing time by 33.8 %.

Given the influence of uneven plate spacing and the other factors discussed above on the freezing time of individual product blocks, the average freezing time for each test was calculated as the mean of the freezing times of all product blocks, as shown in Table 3, providing a comprehensive and representative overview of the freezing time under each test condition. The average freezing time in Test 03 exceeded that in Test 02, which in turn was longer than in Test 01, despite the three tests having comparable average evaporation temperatures. This trend can be primarily attributed to the reduced CR applied in Tests 02 and 03, along with secondary influences from variations in initial product temperature, slight differences in hydraulic pressure exerted on the products, and minor carton deformations.

Fig. 13. Evolution of the power consumption (W) in Tests 02, 04, and 05.

Fig. 14. Evolution of the COPs in Tests 01–05.

5.2. Thermal performance of the plate freezing system

Fig. 12 presents the instantaneous freezing load and power consumption in Test 02. The freezing load was maximal at the initial stage of the process, coinciding with the greatest temperature difference between the refrigerant and the product, which facilitated intensive heat transfer from the product to the refrigerant. As this temperature difference diminished over the course of the operation, the driving force for heat transfer decreased correspondingly, resulting in a progressive decline in the freezing load throughout the process. The variation in power consumption followed the same trend as the freezing load, declining throughout the freezing process.

Fig. 13 compares the power consumption in Tests 02, 04, and 05. Power consumption increased at lower evaporation temperatures due to the greater system temperature lift and the associated rise in compressor pressure ratio. Furthermore, the larger temperature difference between the plate surface and the product enhanced the freezer's evaporation capacity, leading to higher CO₂ vapor mass flow rates and, consequently, greater energy consumption. The CO₂ refrigeration system is equipped with three compressors connected in parallel and operating in sequence, providing a maximum volumetric capacity of 76.2 m³/h. If the system is at its maximum cooling capacity, all three compressors operate. At lower cooling load, the third or both the third and second compressors may remain on standby, with the first and second, or only the first compressor, in operation. In the present freezing tests, the first and second compressor were in operation. During the final stage of freezing in Test 04 and the latter half of the freezing process in Test 05, the declining cooling load approached the upper limit of the first compressor's capacity. As a result, the second compressor was intermittently switched on and off, leading to fluctuations in both the CO₂ mass flow rate and the system's freezing load. To mitigate this instability, the evaporation temperature was lowered by 2 °C to slightly increase the cooling capacity, thereby ensuring simultaneous operation of the first and second compressors throughout the tests. As a result, the declining trend of power consumption was less pronounced in the final stage of Test 04 and the latter half of Test 05. Given that the instantaneous power consumption of the freezing system was derived by applying a fixed isentropic efficiency for each test, the results presented in the plots might exhibit minor discrepancies relative to the true operational values on account of this constraint.

Fig. 14 illustrates the variation in system COP across the tests, and the cumulative COP of each test is listed in Table 3. The COPs of Tests 01–03 were closely aligned, with cumulative COPs ranging from 2.45 to 2.50, and no clear influence of CR was observed. Overall, the system COPs in Tests 01–03 were lower than those in Tests 04–05, which had cumulative COPs of 3.03 and 3.55, respectively, reflecting the effect of reduced temperature lift of the CO₂ system at higher evaporation temperatures. A corresponding decline in COP was observed during the final stage of Test 04 and the latter half of Test 05, when the evaporation temperature was decreased by 2 °C.

Specific energy consumption is defined as the energy required to freeze 1 kg of product from its initial to target temperature, with the calculated values for each test summarized in Table 3. The freezing time used in the calculation corresponded to the longest duration observed in each test, i.e., when the final product block reached the target core temperature. As discussed previously, the use of fixed isentropic efficiency values for each test may induce minor discrepancies between the calculated specific energy consumption results and the actual operational values due to this constraint. No substantial differences in specific energy consumption were observed across tests with varying evaporation temperatures. Although higher evaporation temperatures improved system performance and reduced energy demand, the freezing process was significantly prolonged. As a result, the gains in system efficiency were offset by the extended freezing time, leading to comparable specific energy consumptions across the tests. Tests 02–03 exhibited higher values than the others, which may be attributed to their lower CRs, which likely extended the freezing duration. Nevertheless, excessively high CRs should be avoided. In industrial applications, where the CO₂ supply mass flow rate is typically high to meet freezing demand, pump power consumption cannot be ignored and increases with CR, leading to a slight reduction in COP. Furthermore, high CRs can cause high pressure drops both in the CO₂ return line and across the freezer. In addition to CR, factors such as the initial product temperature, hydraulic pressure applied to each block, product placement, and minor deformations of the apple juice cartons all influenced both freezing time and specific energy consumption. Moreover, since the plate freezer operated in an ambient environment, heat losses to the surroundings were included in the calculated specific energy consumption. For future studies or industrial applications, insulating the outer surfaces of the top and bottom plates is recommended to minimize heat loss.

Table 4
Measured freezing time for different types of fish products.

Test No.	Product	T_{Start} (°C)	$T_{e,ave}$ (°C)	Freezing time (min)
A	Whole herring	0 – 1.5	–48.5	222
	Herring fillets	0 – 1.5		206
B	Whole mackerel	6.5 – 9	–47.3	216
	Whole herring	1 – 7.5		380
C	Herring fillets	0 – 5		205
	Whole mackerel	5 – 6	–47.6	170
	Whole herring	3 – 5		190
D	Herring fillets	2 – 5		136
	Salmon fillets	4 – 6.5	–39.5	389
	Salmon portions	3.5 – 9		516 (–16 °C)

To evaluate the GHG emissions of the plate freezing system, CO₂-equivalent values for electricity were calculated for Norwegian (NO) and European (EU) scenarios. For the NO case, a CO₂ emission factor of 50 g CO₂-eq. kWh⁻¹ was applied, based on the range reported by Clauß, et al. (Clauß et al., 2019). In the EU case, a factor of 210 g CO₂-eq. kWh⁻¹ was used, according to European energy consumption data from the European Environment Agency (European Environment Agency, 2024). The specific GHG emissions for each test are summarized in Table 3. For freezing 1 kg of apple juice cartons, the CO₂-equivalent emissions ranged from 3.18 to 4.88 g in the Norwegian scenario and from 13.3 to 20.5 g in the EU scenario.

5.3. Freezing time measured for fish products

Freezing times were measured for various fish products at different evaporation temperatures, following industrial partner specifications, with the results serving as a reference for industrial operations. Test details and the corresponding freezing times for each product are summarized in Table 4, which reports the shortest freezing times recorded in each case. The fish products after freezing are illustrated in Fig. 15.

The freezing times recorded at three measurement points for each block in Test A are presented in Fig. 16. Freezing times for whole herring ranged from 222 to 280 min, while those for fillets ranged from 206 to 255 min. The shorter freezing times of fillets were primarily due to their smaller individual volume, which enabled more compact packing, reduced void space, improved thermal contact, and facilitated more efficient heat conduction.

In Tests B and C, the more tightly packed blocks exhibited shorter freezing times as a result of improved thermal contact with the plates. The freezing times reported in Table 4 correspond to the shortest times measured from these tightly packed blocks. However, overly compact

packaging of fresh fish may negatively affect its taste and appearance after freezing due to excessive pressure, so maintaining a certain void space is necessary to ensure product quality and market acceptance. Again, herring fillet blocks had shorter freezing times compared to whole mackerel and whole herring blocks—205 min and 136 min for the 100 mm and 75 mm frame height tests, respectively—due to their higher packing density.

The temperature evolution over time for one fully filled salmon fillet block and one salmon portion block in Test D is illustrated in Fig. 17. Compared to the freezing times measured at the centre of the salmon fillet block, the temperatures measured at the top and bottom of the block dropped much more rapidly, with corresponding freezing curves appearing more linear over time, attributed to the quick phase change process for the fillets adjacent to the plates. In addition, the freezing time for the portion block was considerably longer. After 516 min, one of the center temperature measurements in the salmon portion block remained at –16 °C, at which point the test was terminated. This extended freezing time was attributed to the loose packing of portions within the cardboard box, as the mass of the portion blocks was substantially lower than that of fully filled fillet blocks of identical box dimensions. As shown in Fig. 15, the loosely arranged portions created substantial void space, thereby diminishing heat transfer efficiency. Nevertheless, this higher void space allowed the portions to retain a fresher appearance after freezing, with color closer to that prior to freezing than observed in the fillets.

5.4. Simulation results for freezing time

The numerical model proposed in Section 4 was validated against experimental data for the freezing of apple juice cartons and herring fillets. The simulated temperature evolution for Tests 02, 04, and 05 was compared with the experimentally measured temperatures of the fastest-freezing blocks, as illustrated in Fig. 18. Blocks with the shortest freezing times are considered to have the best thermal contact with the plate surfaces and to be least affected by the uneven plate spacing induced by the hydraulic pressure, and are therefore expected to correspond most closely with the simulation results. Therefore, the temperature measurements from these blocks were used to validate the numerical model. Overall, the simulated freezing times closely matched the shortest observed freezing times, with three distinct freezing stages apparent in each simulated temperature curve. However, the model consistently underestimated the duration of the initial freezing stage, likely because it considers only product mass and neglects the effect of product height. Consequently, the simulated center temperature dropped rapidly from the start of freezing, whereas in the experiments the product center

Fig. 15. Test fish products after freezing.

Fig. 16. Evolution of the center temperatures of the test products measured during Test A, as well as the simulated center temperature of herring fillets.

temperature decreased only slightly initially due to heat conduction through its thickness.

Fig. 16 shows the simulated temperature evolution of herring fillets in Test A. Herring fillets were selected to validate the numerical model due to their more compact packing and uniform arrangement within the block compared to whole fish, which better approximates the homogeneous material assumption used in the model. The simulated temperature evolution generally agreed with the experimental results, with the simulated freezing time closely matching the measurement result at Location 3. As observed in the apple juice simulations, the freezing time during the initial stage was slightly underestimated by the model.

6. Conclusions

This study experimentally investigated the performance of a plate freezing system employing CO₂ as the refrigerant, designed for the freezing of fish and meat in food processing. The system incorporated an

industrial-scale horizontal plate freezer integrated into a dedicated CO₂ refrigeration unit. The shared central CO₂ system can provide cooling capacity of 100 kW at evaporation temperature between $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Five tests were conducted for the freezing of apple juice cartons (serving as dummy loads) under different evaporation temperatures and circulation rates. Results demonstrated that reducing the evaporation temperature from $-36.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Test 05) to $-48.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Test 01) shortened the average freezing time by 35.3%. The COP of the plate freezing system decreased markedly with decreasing evaporation temperature, primarily due to the increased temperature lift and compressor pressure ratio of the CO₂ refrigeration system. However, specific energy consumption was not significantly affected by evaporation temperatures, as efficiency gains at higher evaporation temperatures were offset by the longer freezing times. As the instantaneous power consumption of the freezing system was determined using constant isentropic efficiencies for each test owing to the use of a shared central CO₂ system, minor discrepancies

Fig. 17. Evolution of the temperature measured at different locations of the salmon fillet and salmon portion blocks in Test D.

might exist between the calculated energy consumption results and the actual operational values due to this constraint.

Furthermore, lower CR values were observed associated with longer freezing time and higher specific energy consumption, underscoring the importance of optimizing CR to improve operational efficiency and minimize both energy demand and associated GHG emissions. Specific GHG emissions for freezing 1 kg of apple juice cartons resulted in 3.18–4.88 g CO₂-eq in the Norwegian scenario and 13.3–20.5 g CO₂-eq in the EU scenario.

Freezing trials with fish products revealed clear effects of packaging and product arrangement. Under identical operating conditions, herring fillets exhibited the shortest freezing times compared to whole herring and whole mackerel, owing to their more compact packing and improved thermal contact. Similarly, salmon portions required substantially longer freezing times than salmon fillets, primarily due to looser packing and larger void spaces. The results from freezing tests with apple juice cartons and fish products highlight the importance of

uniform plate contact, appropriate packaging material and method, and optimized product void space.

A dynamic numerical model of the plate freezing system was established to support system design and optimization, and to serve as a freezing-time estimation tool for industrial implementation. The model was validated against experimental data for the freezing of apple juice cartons and herring fillets. The simulated temperature profiles exhibited good agreement with the measurements, and the predicted freezing times closely matched the shortest durations observed in each test.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that the CO₂-based plate freezing system, operating at evaporation temperatures as low as –50 °C, can achieve both high operational and energy efficiency, making it a sustainable solution for freezing applications in fish and meat processing. Future work will aim to enhance the stability of the freezing system by optimizing compressor control strategies, systematically evaluating the influence of packaging materials, quantifying the effects of void space on freezing efficiency and product quality, and characterizing and

Fig. 18. Comparison of measured and simulated temperature evolution during Tests 02, 04, and 05.

minimizing heat losses during operation. In addition, the numerical model will be further refined through the inclusion of additional factors such as product block height, void space, pressure losses, and packaging characteristics to provide a reference for industrial applications.

Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT in order to improve language and spell-check the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Nomenclature

Latin symbols		Abbreviations	
h	enthalpy, kJ/kg	COP	coefficient of performance
\dot{m}	mass flow rate, kg/s	CR	circulation rate
P	pressure, bar	GHG	greenhouse gas
Q	freezing load, kW	GWP	global warming potential
T	temperature, °C	ODP	ozone depletion potential
U	Uncertainty		
W	power consumption, kW	Subscripts	
X	measured variable	ave	average
Y	evaluated quantity	com	compressor
		cum	cumulative
		e,ave	average evaporation
		start	start temperature
Greek symbols			
η_{isen}	isentropic efficiency, -		

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Shuai Ren: Writing – original draft, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Patrick Hadamitzky:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Armin Hafner:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Kristina Norne Widell:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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